

Deliverable 3.3

MVP Technical Platform

Work Package: WP3. Technical development and repurposing of games

Grant Agreement Number: 101094766

Due date of deliverable: 30/04/2024

Actual submission date: 30/04/2024

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Dissemination Level: public (PU)

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Deliverable Information

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Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This document describes the Minimum Viable Platforms DiBL and PlayMob that are available for pilots from M18 in the GREAT project.
Keywords	Quiz, survey, dilemma, MVP, platform, data, dashboard
Statement of originality	<p>This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.</p>

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
0.1	20/03/2024	Draft 0.1 document created
0.2	11/04/2024	Draft 0.2 document created (PlayMob part not included)
0.3	17/04/2024	Draft 0.3 consolidated comments from reviewers
0.4	26/04/2024	Draft 0.4 included PlayMob sections
1.0	30/04/2024	Final draft completed

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development
CO	Confidential
DMP	Data Management Plan
DeLA	Data-enriched Learning Analytics
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMB	Executive Management Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
Live Ops	Live Operations
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PMC	Project Management Committee
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SC	Scientific Committee
TRL	Technology Readiness Level (1= low / 9=high)
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This document describes the Minimum Viable Platforms DiBL and PlayMob that are available for pilots from M18 in the GREAT project after running the first cycle of pilots, where important learnings have been made to adjust and extend the existing platforms to support future cycles. This deliverable describes the realisation of what was specified in [D3.1](#), where most of the features envisioned are available in the MVP. The key areas that are still in prototype stage are for DiBL a more user-friendly visual editor, templates to speed up creation of case studies, and further examination of Data-enriched Learning Analytics. For PlayMob, we presented three key areas of the platform (survey tech, distribution, and data management). These allow for an initial set of survey campaigns with games industry partners to collect diversely segmented data at scale for later analysis and optimisation of the system. It is envisioned that further elements will be developed based on the requirements of the project.

	PlayMob: Survey Tech (+survey)	DiBL: Dilemma (+survey)
Summary	Quick single-player gamified survey solution.	Facilitated synchronous multiplayer dilemma-based game solution.
Players per session	1	6-50
Context of use	Online	F2F classroom, or video conference
Facilitated	No	Yes
Duration	1-2 minutes	30-120 minutes
Flow	Linear	Branching
Complexity	Low	Medium
Scoring	1 variable	10+ variables
Anonymous data	Yes	Yes (but can be changed)
Research style	Quantitative	Quantitative and qualitative
Team play	No	Yes
Best for	Scale and speed	In-depth exploration & discussion
Reach	Millions	Thousands

Table 1: Overview of the two solutions available in the GREAT project

The flexible and agile approach we envisioned in [D2.1](#) and [D3.1](#) have been successful. In particular, it is very useful to accommodate the uncertainty around diverse stakeholder profiles and use case scenarios of stakeholders in the GREAT project. However, it has also proven challenging to both the delivery of case studies, while developing a method and extending the platform. Still, this approach will continue going forward.

2. Brief introduction to this deliverable

Research and innovation in the GREAT project will provide new insights into the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU for the benefit of society. A key part is to repurpose and extend the two existing platforms DiBL and PlayMob to support this. As part of the GREAT project, we will make both platforms easier to use and provide supporting materials and well-defined methods to create user and stakeholder content, and new enhanced features to support the project case studies. This document describes how we have repurposed and extended the two current platforms delivered by PlayMob (Survey tech engine) and Serious Games Interactive (DiBL: Dilemma-based-learning Games) to serve stakeholders and case studies in GREAT.

Through the GREAT research methodology utilising the two game platforms, it is expected to make an important contribution to democracy education and help promote social engagement and low-threshold political participation of citizens in the EU and partner countries. Up-to-date details of GREAT activities are available on the project website www.greatproject.gq

It's important to stress that these are not new products but are rather based on existing platforms that can be adjusted and extended based on what insights have been gained through the case study cycles described in [D2.1](#) and further work in WP2 and WP4 and that will further evolve as new case studies are completed.

The two platforms are already supporting more elaborate case studies (e.g. the Green Jobs DiBL case study and Rooftops DiBL case study, which will be launched in May 2024), and several new case studies are also in progress.

3. Overall objectives for WP3

This deliverable describes the second step in WP3. In [D3.1](#), we described the goals for new developments in the platforms, whereas this deliverable (D3.3) presents how these have actually been implemented. The overarching goals remain as follows:

- 1). Repurposing existing platforms for policy-makers' needs that will be identified throughout the 5 cycles of WP4 (see [D4.1](#)).
- 2). Creating one game in DiBL or PlayMob for each of the case studies of WP2. At least one for each of the 5 cycles.
- 3). Gathering and visualising data from each case study to WP4 and WP5.

4. Agile methodology

As planned, we have used an agile methodology. It may be that the method is too agile, rather than less, than the method and approach described in [D4.2](#), as it was still crystallising at the time of writing, and being adopted by GREAT project partners.

The experience from the cycles so far shows that the agile approach, where we emphasise adaptability, collaboration, and co-creation is critical because there are still many interconnected moving parts.

Figure 1: Shows the agile process

During the development of the MVP of the platforms, we have followed the key principles described below. For example, in DiBL we have made regular updates 1-2 times per month on a staging server that have been shared internally with SGI, and key partners that were requesting the features. After these have been tested, and optimised, it has been rolled out to production within the following 1-2 weeks:

- *Iterative development*: Instead of planning the entire project upfront, Agile development allows for continuous iteration and improvement, where we constantly de-risk the project and incorporate the latest learnings.
- *Stakeholder collaboration & co-creation*: Agile encourages close collaboration between developers and stakeholders, including researchers, policy-makers,

and end-users. Regular feedback from these stakeholders helps ensure that the project aligns with the intended goals.

- *Adaptability*: Agile embraces that requirements and priorities may change over time. Teams are encouraged to be flexible and responsive to these changes, adjusting their focus in each sprint as needed.
- *Cross-functional Teams*: Agile promotes the idea of self-organising, cross-functional teams that allows us to leverage the full GREAT consortium's skills and expertise.
- *Continuous delivery*: Agile emphasises delivering functional, tested components at the end of each sprint. This ensures that progress is measurable and allows for the early identification of any issues that may arise. This is critical also to ensure collaboration and co-creation.
- *Regular reflection and improvement*: At the end of each sprint, the team reflects on what went well and what could be improved. This continuous feedback loop helps refine processes and enhances the overall efficiency of the development effort.

The agile praxis have also included challenges especially around navigating between different agendas with not always overlapping interests.

- Collaboration with external stakeholders around specific domains, purposes and target groups where the tools need to fit.
- Defining, refining and documenting the research process.
- Developing an overarching and standardised methodology that will work across multiple case studies and after the project ends.
- Designing and creating specific case studies in the platforms, where some features are ready and others are still being developed and/or tested.
- Extending and repurposing the existing platforms to serve current and future needs better.

It is still too early to conclude on negative and positive practice in this regard. However, the agile approach is the only feasible approach with this degree of uncertainty anticipated in the project case studies cycles.

5. Technical specification of DiBL: Dilemma-based Learning platform

Current capabilities and usage in GREAT activities

DiBL is a proprietary platform built by partner SGI to make dilemma-based learning games that enable engaging and inclusive facilitator-driven offline or online collaborative experiences. It already had numerous features ready when the GREAT project started - a holistic platform that enabled users to create a dilemma game, launch it and gather data.

Figure 2: Shows the facilitator screen and mobile phone, whereas Figure 3: shows the current creator

However, it became clear that there was a need for a number of iterations to perfect that towards different use cases being uncovered across policy-makers.

Below, we have chosen to keep the overall description from [D3.1](#) for DiBL to better contextualise and clearly show where the solution has been expanded. It does not cover all the finer details and optimisations but it does cover the key enhancements.

This report covers DiBL Production release-608 (11th April 2024). There is a small quick video to demonstrate core functionality and the two most recent cases here: <https://vimeo.com/941148677/5da9168c6a?share=copy>

All new features and improvements are currently on TRL7 but close to TRL8 as we are implementing case studies in Cycle #2.

1. Game player: The end-user experience consists of a game screen for the facilitator, where the game progression is controlled, shared game content is shown, as well as the effect of participant decisions. There is also a separate game screen for each participant, where they will receive participant-specific information and make participant choices.

Key enhancements: After several reports from users, and especially issues with older devices, a number of optimisations were introduced.

- *Counter removed:* Through users' testing, we realised that the facilitator and participants became very confused with a counter that constantly updated relating to whether participants were active and not. This means that the number of participants in a session would vary if a participant device went in sleep mode. This confused some participants because they were still present physically but since their device went to sleep, the counter suggested otherwise. We changed this so that the counter now only shows how many participants have actually contributed, and then we assume and anticipate that the facilitator and participants have a good idea of how many should have responded.
- *PDF facilitator export:* We have created an option where you can download anonymous data on response across the case study at the end, as a facilitator. Thus, you can continue to work with that after the session has ended.
- *Intelligent scaling for different screens:* We have introduced better support for different screens and projectors as the variety was larger than previously envisioned. This means that we can better serve older projectors and +4K projectors. This makes it easier for the facilitators to get started, and not risk having issues with viewing content that could especially be an issue for participants with visual impairment.
- *Fall back for memory issues:* We uncovered issues on some special use cases, where facilitators idle longer than previously use cases. This increases the risk that participants switch windows and in parallel use system resources that can log them out of DiBL. This especially happens if using incognito on older devices with limited RAM (e.g. Iphone SE, Safari).
- *Wake lock SignalR feature:* On newer devices, it is possible to keep the connection with the facilitator/server through a special feature that we implemented because it provides a more seamless experience, where you are less inclined to be put in sleep mode and have to wake up the device. Also although bugs are rare they are very often related to coming online from sleep mode, so it also made the solution overall much more robust.

All new features in the game creator below are needed to be implemented in the game player. However, in order to keep it clear and simple, they are described below.

2. Game creator: Here, users utilise a visual creator to set up their dilemma games. The system offers support for the following functionalities that can be utilised in the design of case activities, as follows:

- Single-player & Multi-player choice
- Free-text and rating of free text
- Teams & roles to use throughout game
- Variables to store and use throughout
- Logic & branching to control flow
- Text, images and video to support experience
- Styling to make the experience look like your own solution

Figure 4: Detailed zoom-in on the DiBL creator showing a new sentence cloud in the middle, and other interaction features on the right panel.

DiBL key adjustments and extensions

- *New languages:* In DiBL we now not only have English, German, Danish and Greek but also Spanish, Portuguese, French, Dutch, Italian, Norwegian, Finnish,

Swedish, Polish and Czech. This will allow us to more easily support the use of NGOs across the EU. We can easily add additional languages if required in future cycles.

- *Sentence / word cloud:* We have developed a classic word cloud visualisation and a unique variant supporting sentences that can support longer suggestions shared in plenary.
- *Image question:* We can now ask questions with an image and just not text that provides variety, and broader coverage of topics to ask.
- *Funnel logic for workshops / open approach:* We can now ask open questions and the top rated ones are shared for final prioritisation by participants.
- *Open facilitator question:* The facilitator can create answer options during a session that reflects the key discussion in that particular session.
- *Re-vote feature so you can revisit a node:* We add a key ability so you can go back in the flow, and revisit previous questions and choices, which is key to build more complex and efficient DiBL structures.
- *Drop-down feature for facilitator and participants:* Addition of a feature so you can choose from more options easily.
- *Solution for standard GIF animations:* We have made a standard solution and set.
- *Better visual layout:* With its own colours, font size and font colour across all pages to improve branding.
- *Expanded and more flexible free-text field:* You can now more easily select text, and put in longer strings of text.
- *Added number of options in a dilemma:* Some use cases needed more options to choose from, so we have expanded it, so a dilemma can contain up to 12 options now.

3. Game analytics: Data is stored on an individual (anonymised) level, so the users can see how each individual has chosen. This can be saved as .csv and .xls files.

DiBL key adjustments and extensions

- *API support:* We have enabled support for the API that we will initially use for the LiveOps (see section later in this document). It may also be used for cycles later to display more specific data to policy-makers and organisations.

- *Exporter improvement:* We have added differentiation of type of output whether it is missing data or not filled out data. Also, we added a column to summarise other columns..
- *User-friendly dashboard for high-level data:* We created a dashboard that can quickly visualise key data for administrators. This also created the foundation for sharing this on a shared GREAT LiveOps board.

Figure 5. Screenshot of DiBL live Dashboard

4. Admin system: This handles the state of a DiBL case to make it go online, manage files and assign users.

There have so far not needed any changes to this beyond a few optimisations and bug fixes to the file manager.

The major features that are not currently included in the MVP is listed below:

- a new visual flow creator that makes it easier and more intuitive to make DiBLs (prototype stage) (Current TRL4).
- templates functionality that makes it faster to make DiBLs, and support different didactic approaches and use cases for faster adaptation based on best practice in case studies conducted in cycle (prototype stage) (Current TRL4).

- DeLA extension to explore better learning analytics and AI (concept stage) (Current TRL1).

We have not added the free tier to access the GREAT case study as that will first be relevant when the game launches. However, this will be a seamless and quick task.

6. Technical specification of PlayMob: An insights quiz game platform

The PlayMob Platform engages gamers internationally throughout the project on the topic of the climate crisis by leveraging existing hit mobile games, as a channel to have a two-way conversation with the global audience, reaching all corners of the planet, anonymously and privately including reaching minority and underrepresented groups.

The platform has three key components that have been utilised and expanded throughout the first cycles, and will continued to do so in the next cycles, and may even have variations depending on the scenario and stakeholders.

Figure 6. Visualisation of the life cycle of PlayMob

The three key areas of the PlayMob platform are *Survey Tech*, *Distribution* and *Data Management*, as described below:

1. **Survey Tech** - a customisable survey system which can be deployed and managed at scale with multi-language support and data segmentation by granular distribution channels.

This is the engagement tool which will be deployed to engage, gather anonymous insights and learn more about the player. Using a custom survey engine and drawing on pre-existing datasets, themes such as transport, energy, farms and food, nature, protecting people and the green economy will be tackled. The survey format also appeals to a broad range of gamers, and the popularity and familiarity of the selected engagement format will ensure high participation and engagement rates. Question design and development will be supported by a team of experts, which will include researchers well-versed in the principles of behavioural psychology.

PlayMob Survey Tech MVP

PlayMob has created an updated survey/quiz system with a streamlined interface designed to rapidly capture sentiments and knowledge on a topic within a few minutes or less with an eye on large scale distribution through social channels and in-game promotions by the games industry. The MVP features:

- Intro page with survey overview
- Flexible number of questions/answers (including demographics) derived from the survey configuration system
- Support for single/multiple choice answers
- Scalable data collection infrastructure with segmentation by survey, partner source
- Preferred language detection (with survey translations into ca. 10 languages) and logging
- Automatic tagging of country/city data from the respondent
- Survey pages optimised for fast page loads globally
- Post survey landing page with personality types based on responses
- A/B testing to optimise the User Interface, increase engagement and completion rates
- Basic duplicate session identification and prevention methods

This MVP has been used in two trial runs, one with a games partner and another as paid promotion in Instagram ads. Responses from over 12,000 user sessions validated it as a successful and effective way to collect data for the GREAT Project.

Survey Tech Roadmap

In order to improve our ability to collect accurate data, appeal to external stakeholders to collaborate with and streamline the workflow of conducting surveys, we have identified a few key areas. Some of these features still need further review, to determine if they can significantly positively impact the project based on the number of surveys we will run and the level of effort involved to modify the current survey tech. The features are as follows:

Freeform text input for questions: Collect more nuanced user input beyond multiple choice answers. To be used sparingly, to avoid affecting survey completion rate.

Question and answer order randomisation: Improve response rate to all questions and avoid order related bias of responses. Flexibility should still exist to allow groups of questions in a specific order.

Intro page co-branding: Custom logo usage and other text/branding per source and distribution channel of a survey, to acknowledge survey promotion partners.

Custom post-survey pages: Customize the page after a survey with bespoke links and other content, depending on the survey, source and distribution, to accommodate different goals per cycle or promotional partner.

Question branching: Certain question answers can lead to different questions. To be implemented, if the need arises.

Content and config settings CMS: Manage survey configuration settings and content (plus their translations) in a more convenient way, so that more project members can manage this information and set up/update surveys.

Live preview: Preview changes to survey content and config settings before a deployment.

Survey Tech MVP Screenshots

The following screenshots are taken from a pilot survey:

https://survey.planetplay.com/survey/gci_2/?source=great_d33

Figure 7. Survey intro page

Figure 8. Survey question (single choice)

PLANETPLAY

Transport

To address the climate crisis, how should your country improve transport?

Choose all that apply.

- Use more clean electric cars and buses, or bicycles
- Transport goods on planes, ships, trains and trucks that run on clean energy
- Improve the design and planning of cities and rural communities
- None of the above

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Figure 9. Survey question (multiple choice)

PLANETPLAY

Age:

Under 18	18 - 35
36 - 59	60+

Gender:

M	F	X
---	---	---

11/12

Figure 10. Survey demographics questions

Figure 11. Post survey page

The second key area of the PlayMob platform is Distribution, as follows:

2. **Distribution** - via in-game links or in-game advertising space. The main channel to reach a diverse and representative audience will be through existing hit mobile games such as Candy Crush, Subway Surfers and many more. The power of this approach is shown by the distribution by PlayMob of 'Mission 1.5' to 33 million people across 50 countries in 22 languages.

Below is a screenshot of how one of the first Survey Tech powered climate surveys was promoted (via a QR code) in console and PC platforms:

Figure 12. In-game survey promotion by game studio (Hirez Studios/SMITE)

The third key area of the PlayMob platform is Data Management, as follows:

3. **Data Management** - collect and manage data from various distribution channels and present it in an internal dashboard for the project partners. This LiveOps overview gives access to a basic, initial summary of data collected so far and details the steps necessary to obtain it for in-depth analysis.

Data collected includes:

- a. answers given to a set of questions, and
- b. which host game the player came from,
- c. which platform (if not a game) the player comes from, such as a specific website or social media channel, and
- d. whether the player clicked to learn/do more.

Figure 13. LiveOps Dashboard activity KPIs

Figure 14. LiveOps Dashboard answer summaries

Figure 15. LiveOps Dashboard geo data breakdown (countries)

To conclude, actions and data are tracked in the PlayMob platform in real-time, enabling optimisation and rapid course correction, if required. The methodology applies equally to broad as well as highly focused audiences and can be deployed with either the rigour of a national poll, or by gathering realistic sample sizes based on required confidence levels.

7. Progression on Tasks and Deliverables

Based on the timeplan defined in the grant agreement, we have specified below the work in [D3.1](#) that covers the whole of WP3. Below is the overview of the current WP3 gantt chart. Overall the activities are almost on track. We had a small delay because we prioritised finishing some specific games for the case studies for the cycle #2 before finishing the MVPs, so we are 1-2 months behind the table shown below. We have also switched some components around and therefore have delayed a few MVP features for DiBL that were not required in the first 3 case studies. PlayMob have prioritised the LiveOps dashboard higher than the new MVP version of PlayMob platform because that can be used additionally as foundation for their future work (PlayMob V1 and later versions).

GANTT CHART WP3 TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENT (WP3.3)										
				Jan '24					July '24	
				12	13	14	15	16	17	18
				LEAD	Wing	Support				
D3.3: MVP technical platform										
Workshop Copenhagen Cycle #1 insights	S	G	I	PM	All		X			
DiBL V1 - ready for next cycles	S	G	I	PM			X			
DiBL Case studies cycle #2 and #3	S	G	I	PM	ZSI, FU, UoB				X	
PM V1 - ready for next cycle	PM	S	G	I			X			
PM Case studies cycle #2 and #3	PM	S	G	I	ZSI, FU, UoB					X
Workshop Cycle #2 and #3 insights	PM	S	G	I	All					X
D3.3 READY	S	G	I	PM				X		(X)

Table 2. GANTT chart of WP3 for D3.3

8. Quality Assurance Procedures

In the DiBL games, we use the X-Ray test suite in JIRA to manage automated testing, thus reducing the need for manual testing, and have a smooth CI/CD process (Continuous Integration/Continuous development). We use Playwright to run the test on the frontend.

Playmob uses TypeScript to catch some problems within the development IDE. Code changes are reviewed via git pull requests by the technical lead and then tested by several other team members on a test environment before they are integrated into the production branch. A CI/CD step ensures that a new release builds properly before a deployment to production. Additionally, survey specific configuration data is validated to ensure that there are no inconsistencies (e.g. questions with no answers).

9. Roles, Responsibilities and Collaboration

Playmob Survey Tech: PlayMob & PlanetPlay

Jude Ower, CEO, Playmob

Joost Schuur, Technical Integration manager, PlayMob

Sandro Oliveira, Technical Lead, PlanetPlay

Richard Vignais, Head of Product, PlanetPlay

DiBL: Serious Games Interactive

Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen, CEO Serious Games Interactive

Martin Lund, CTO DiBL

Case Studies

ZSI, UNIR, FU and UoB: Will be responsible for creating the Green Jobs DiBL case study based on the work done in WP4.

Figure 16: Live version of of Green Jobs DiBL case study to be rolled out in cycle #2 in Austria co-created with ZSI and the Austrian Klimafonds¹

¹ <https://www.klimafonds.gv.at/>

Figure 17: Live version of of Rooftops DiBL case study to be rolled out in cycle #2 in Cyprus, co-created with Frederick University and the Urban Gorillas²

10. Data Protection and Privacy

10.1. Data protection

We follow a number of best practices in this project. For example, the principles and guidelines that OWASP contributed to and can be applied to data protection and privacy practices within web applications. Note that OWASP is an online community that produces freely available articles, methodologies, documentation, tools and technologies). The principles and guidelines are presented below:

1. Data collected by the Survey Tech system is never personally identifiable.
2. Least privilege roles approach - only a small technical team has direct access to the database systems that hold the data.
3. Testing and production use separate database environments.
4. Access to production environments (and the ability to generate further access) is only assigned as absolutely needed.

² <https://urbangorillas.org/>

5. Access to third party tools (e.g. Tinybird) only available through permission-based, named (not shared) accounts (subject to their strict password policies etc).
6. When shared via an API with the dashboard e.g., authorisation is required by the API endpoint.
7. Access by outside partners is limited to only their relevant surveys and regulated by named accounts.
8. Public data is only ever made available for very tailored purposes (e.g. when creating a highly specific data panel for a public web page).

10.2. Data privacy

We follow the principles described in [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook, relating to collecting consent for participation but in general all data is anonymous on the platforms. For evaluation purposes, we may add a key so that we can connect a response in the platform with responses in other survey tools. As such the data will be pseudonymized, and participants will need to be informed.

10.3. Ethics

We have followed the principles laid out in [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook, in relation to research integrity and good research practice, 2) Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.

The responsibility for the research ethics using the technology in this deliverable, lies with the Academic Lead of each case study, as stated in deliverable [D4.2 GREAT Case Study Plan](#). This is an area that the technology partners will be guided by the Academic Partner to ensure the highest standards of ethics are adhered to.

11. Open Access, Open Research Data & IPR

In general, we will make as much material and data available as possible.

11.1. Open access to tools & games

- The proprietary platform from DiBL and Playmob remains the property of the partners that brought it into the projects.
- The project-specific material will be made publicly available.
- Any open source release would not get access to the GREAT Project's infrastructure used by our surveys. For example, this means that they would need to set up their own Tinybird workspace to collect data.

11.2. Open access data

- All data is fully anonymized, and will be available for open access.
- This access may not be live updating, and instead take the form of a data dump in a git repository.

12. Closing remarks

The current MVPs serve as a strong starting point but we still expect them to develop more as we get more insights from the current and future cycles, where we gain more insights. As described in [D3.1 Technical Specification](#) and [D2.1 Intervention Design](#), we still aim for a high degree of flexibility in the method, and the accompanying technical platforms.

The current MVP should be seen as a list of features we have validated in the first pilot cycle and that can support at least cycles #2 and #3 but not encompassing all the adaptations we may need to make throughout the project. This depends on the requirements of the policy-maker stakeholders that will be participating and progressing forward. We may see specific requirements that are more project-specific or entirely new features from either policy-makers, domain experts, teachers, citizens or other stakeholders.

